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Designing a Virtual 3D Environment for Learning near the Workplace in SME

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Abstract

Context: The paper is based on the BMBF and ESF-funded research project ‘Ageing-appropriate, process-oriented and interactive further training in SME (API-KMU)’, which is a collaboration between LSWI at the University of Potsdam, the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology KIT’s Institute of Vocational and General Pedagogy, the media design and VR-development company *room* as well as two SMEs to apply the learning environment in the companies. The project aims to develop a virtual learning environment for novices in the job to benefit from the experiences and knowledge of skilled workers. In the paper, we look at research undertaken in one case: a company in natural stone processing (SPP).

Approach/methodology: The research approach is based on the analysis of the work tasks (BAG); two main tasks for learning modules were identified. Semi-structured interviews with staff were done, and the observation of the workplace was both video-recorded. The didactic approach is subject-oriented, referring to self-directed and constructivist learning and shaping principles. These form the basis for the development of a virtual learning environment and training concept, including learning modules for use in SMEs. The learning environment is developed to support the SME’s needs in the onboarding process.

Findings: The analysis of the work process of mitre gluing was followed by the development of a so-called ‘competence spider’, a tool to support both self-reflection and external assessment in the context of employee interviews. It supports an open dialogue structured along the competences identified and required for the job and how those are perceived by the employee him/herself (internally) and by the supervisor (externally).

Conclusion: The analysis of the work tasks (BAG) is a helpful instrument for both identifying skills and competences required and for developing criteria for a training concept. Complex work processes can be broken down into single activities to be used for self- and external assessment in an employee interview. The design process of a pedagogically shaped virtual learning environment is a complex and challenging process, which needs to be designed carefully

with regard to the didactic approach and its requirements. The learning contents can be mediated and supported through animation videos.

Keywords: VR learning, SME, near the workplace, professional training, situated learning

1 Introduction: From the Analysis of Work Tasks Towards the Educational Design of a Responsive Virtual Learning Environment

The overall objective of the project is to develop an age-appropriate, process-oriented and interactive continuing education approach including a toolbox for SMEs as well as an approach to secure and transfer tacit knowledge by means of a VR-supported learning and tutoring system based on didactic principles by the SMEs themselves.

In the following, we discuss the process starting from the analysis of work tasks towards the derived design of a responsive virtual learning environment consisting of a 3D space and online learning platform. The paper is based on the BMBF-funded project API-KMU (acronym) which looks at ‘Ageing-appropriate, process-oriented and interactive further training in SME’. The aim of the joint project API-KMU is to develop an age-appropriate, process-oriented and media-based continuing education program in small and medium-sized enterprises SMEs based on didactic considerations for a 3D learning environment. The target group are employees of small and medium-sized enterprises who are to be enabled to develop new competencies and to actively shape and master the challenges of digitalization and demographic change. The concrete results of the joint project are a virtual 3D- learning environment with a Web portal, which serves as an initial orientation during the induction of new employees to support, among other things, the onboarding process of an SME. New employees are given visual opportunities to acquire company knowledge in the virtual learning environment. The transfer of knowledge from experienced employees as well as the transfer of experiential knowledge is to be supported by the digital possibilities of the learning environment. It addresses the target group of employees new to the company, mainly career changers age 30 and older. The learning environment is aimed to support an SME in natural stone processing in the onboarding process.

In the paper, the development process is discussed based on the analysis of work tasks and identified competences required derived from it in the context of mitre glueing in window sill production. The latter is a complex process including a variety of work process knowledge and work experiences to be applied by the worker. How can this process as well as other learning contents related to the work environment such as machines and tools, materials and aids be facilitated when new staff is to be trained and needs to get an appropriate introduction to the company’s most common areas, tasks, and tools in the manufacturing process?

2 Work Task Analysis and Competence Requirements Derived

Competencies only show in action and accordingly can only be observed in action. In order to identify the skills required to carry out the work tasks, the work analysis was selected. The research approach combines the results of the work analysis with video recording and the didactic framework based on subject-oriented, self-directed constructivist elements to be applied in the virtual learning environment.

The analysis of work tasks undertaken in the project was based on the BAG instrument by Haasler (2003) and extended by video records of the work processes and staff interviews at the management and employee level. BAG is an analysis procedure for the identification of work and learning content for the design of vocational training. It includes observation categories such as the workplace and its interfaces in the overall manufacturing process. Further, it contains the categories of business and work process for ‘on-site analysis’ and activity descriptions as well as the work contents, tools, methods and requirements of the skilled work.

As a first step, a typical work situation was recorded on video. In this way, insights into the work process were gained that are difficult to observe. In a second step, the survey team conducted an interview with the respective employee, in which the video-based material serves as a basis for discussion. This way, the work task could be described in detail by the employee and reflection processes about the activity were stimulated. The video observation of the workplace, the documentation of the work process and the analysis of activities aimed to identify the employee's tacit knowledge and level of competence.

The learning modules were then derived from the results of the work task analysis. Different work tasks were identified through the observation of work. Two work processes were defined to be the content of the learning environment. The manual polishing in windowsill production and mitre gluing. From the BAG analysis, however, it has also emerged that another module is relevant for the learning environment and on-boarding process, which generally has to do with knowledge of the machines, production material and tools.

In the paper, we look at the process of mitre glueing which is described in the following, in order to give an overview to estimate the complexity of work tasks to be done. Mitre glueing is a complex process which requires a variety of cognitive, haptic, and visual skills and work experience with the materials are required. The precise perception of the employee is of high importance: Visual and haptic checks of the material, care and precision are required to undertake the work well.

After having carried out 19 different activities related to the work preparation, the actual mitre glueing begins with the application and joining of the mitre surfaces. To do this, the aluminium rail is folded down to the marked position; the adhesive is applied to the mitre surfaces, and the block edge is folded up against the worktop and fixed to the aluminium rail with the existing pieces of adhesive tape. Another 10 steps are to be carried out to finish the process: Those relate to checking, removing and roughening, sanding and cleaning, fixing and turning the product.

After having carried out all the above activities, the final product is ready for storage.

In order to describe the competences to be trained and tested in the virtual environment, the 'competence spider' was developed. It was derived from the work task analysis related to "implementation expertise". It includes the competences required for the planning and implementation of mitre gluing as shown in the Figure 1 and Figure 2 below.

Figure 1

Competence requirements or the planning and implementing of mitre gluing

How well do I fulfil each skill requirement? How well can I carry out the tasks?

I Work preparation

- 1 Read construction plan - check feasibility of the order
- 2 Knowledge of stock check
- 3 Work flow planning (sequences, sequences etc.)
- 4 Knowing the transport conditions (free paths, carrying technique) & transporting the production material
- 5 Know the required work equipment and health & safety regulations

II Specific preparatory work and preliminary considerations regarding the manufacturing product

- 6 Knowledge about material properties (robustness, stability, temperature resistance)
- 7 Checking worktop & block edge for integrity & dimensions.
- 8 Cleaning the pre-product
- 9 Pre-assembly, positioning & accurate fixing of the production object

II Preparation of bonding process

- 10 Knowing the adhesive properties (e. g. discoloration, curing conditions)
- 11 Positioning timing and positioning implementation (support system)

(continued on next page)

12 Correct application of the adhesive tape & knowing its functionality
13 Processing (cutting, roughening, deburring) of the aluminium rails & positioning of the aluminium rails
14 Adhesive production

III Carrying out mitre gluing

15 Exposing the mitre edge
16 Gluing the aluminium rails using silicone
17 Mitre gluing using mixed adhesive
18 Checking the alignment of the aluminium rails
19 Knowing the curing process & its conditions

IV Work process completion

20 Remove final fabricated product from tape pieces
21 Sanding of bottom side & visible side of mitre
22 cleaning of the finished product
23 optical embellishments by means of aluminium tape
24 Prepare finished product for collection

Figure 2

Twenty-four work tasks are shown in the competence spider for self-reflection and assessment in employee interviews

For the learning environment, the 'competence spider' serves as a tool for accessing the learning process in form of an interview, so that self-reflection/evaluation and external assessment can be matched and discussed. The employee is to answer the question of how well his/her competences are already acquired, related to each skill identified.

3 The Didactic Framework

Learning is an active and complex social process. The educational goal to aspire to in the project is the virtual learning environment to facilitate the company's onboarding process

including the support of new employees' orientation in the company and work environment. The aims and observations resulted in a kind of triad that had to be taken into account in the development of a virtual learning environment: The technical development, work design, and the existing or desired competencies of the employees (cp. Baron et al, 2019, p. 6)

The development of a didactic framework for continuous learning was realized according to adult pedagogical principles/guidelines. It includes theoretical approaches such as subject-oriented didactics, constructivist, self-directed, and situated learning near the workplace.

The core of the didactic framework is the support of the employees to cope with daily work and to reflect on the work processes and his/her meaning and competences required in the overall work process. It takes into account the meso- (company) level, including the company's and as well as the micro-level of learning, individual prerequisites in terms of skills, participation and design aspects.

The didactic concept includes learning modules and subordinated learning units based on the identification of knowledge fields, as described in the following:

- Knowledge field 1 deals with Work equipment and production material such as machinery, production material, tools, protective equipment and auxiliary material
- Knowledge field 2 deals with manual polishing of window sills: It addresses an overview of the production process, production certificate, production of the preliminary product, preparation of the "manual polishing" work step
- Knowledge field 3 deals with the complex process of mitre gluing including an overview of the manufacturing process, CAD design and planning

In terms of the didactic concept, the claim was that the learner him/herself becomes a part of the surrounding space, navigating self-directed through it, benefitting from the added value of visual simulations e.g. of different qualities of physical work materials and tools and in-world video streams, rather than being restricted to traditional text-based seminaristic learning arrangements. The aim was not to subordinate the didactic concept to the technical conditions and limitations which came along with in the development phase.

4 The Virtual Learning Environment

VR environments can offer sensory immersion, remote presence, and teleoperations (cp. Laurel, 1993,188). According to Turkle (2009) simulation aims for immersion. The learner him/herself is part of the surrounding, immersive learning space, navigating self-directed through the space, including the added value of visual simulations, e.g. the simulation of different qualities of the physical work materials and tools so that the learner is rather not restricted to traditional text-based seminaristic learning arrangements. However, the educational goal to aspire to in the API-KMU project is a 3D learning space to facilitate new employees' orientation in the company and work environment. As one navigates around these imaginary spaces with different 3D objects, the exploration of the workplace might become an experience for the learner rather than a theoretical perception of the workspace as known from text-based platforms.

From the company's perspective, the 3D learning environment is aimed to facilitate the onboarding processes and the transfer of tacit knowledge and work experience. Tacit knowledge is acquired through active action processes in a lived practice. The development from work experience to work process knowledge has been examined in the context of computer-supported skilled work and vocational learning by Fischer (2000) among others.

The virtual learning environment consists of a Web portal and a 3D world visualizing the SME's main areas such as machines, tools as well as the two work processes identified as learning content. Videos are available, explaining complex processes through animation and moving

images. The Web portal was developed to extend the virtual world and make available materials for learning, printing and storing in one's personal learning space.

The conceptual basis of the 3D models is based on:

- o the elaborated detailed concept of the learning offer at SPP
- o the concrete conceptual plan, which provides information on the learning objective and content, the individual development tasks and the actors involved per knowledge field and the associated learning units.

The Definition of general requirements and functions of the VR environment modelled were to allow for

- an independent, free movement of the user through the VR space.
- Pause function with storage of the intermediate status
- There is no need for a 1:1 faithful reproduction of the SPP production hall.
- Machine systems do not have to be modelled to scale
- Integration of different file formats
- Objects (e.g. machinery) can be provided with annotations (further information) that can be called up by mouse click
- Joint identification of objects relevant for the VR-based learning system together with the project partner SPP (machinery, tools, auxiliary materials, protective equipment and production material, production of the preliminary product, preparation of the work step "gluing in practice")
- Determination of the number of VR rooms required in the learning system:
 - o Room 1: Machine plant room
 - o Room 2: Material storage room
 - o Room 3: Storage room for tools, aids & protective equipment
 - o Room 4: Production room for mitre gluing
- Definition of room-specific requirements (e.g. objects, application conditions etc.) in each case for the individual rooms

The development of a storyboard for the VR environment was done by transferring the identified activities and objects into a VR scenario by means of a storyboard for navigation.

5 Evaluation and Methodology

The research design represents a combination of different survey methods (method mix), combining both qualitative and quantitative methods. Quantitative data will be collected especially in the area of media system-related ergonomic usability research in the Lab of the LSWI.

The concept of the interface emerged from the idea of human-computer interaction and evolved towards the inclusion of the cognitive and the emotional aspects of the user experience (cp. Laurel, 2009, xi). The aim here is to investigate whether the 3D learning environment with the associated website has been implemented in accordance with ergonomic quality criteria (usability) and human-machine-interaction and last not least whether it can be used in a way that promotes learning. E.g. the System Usability Scale (SUS), a method for the quantitative analysis of usability, might be used for this purpose. Since interface problems often are obvious and solutions are usually less obvious, a variety of target groups to test the pilot are included (students, staff, researchers).

The perspective refers to subject-oriented, self-directed, constructivist approaches. The results of the methodological considerations illustrate the necessity of a mix of methods to generate a deeper insight into the work processes (cp. Langemeyer et al 2021, p. 1). The target group – end users of the learning environment – are skilled workers, machine operators,

newcomers to the company, career changers and other company employees who have to take over work tasks or who should perform a similar work activity.

1st quantitative data will be collected in particular in the area of the 3D prototype, the system-related ergonomic usability research at the LSWI Lab.

2nd the qualitative data will be collected at the level of the companies' staff related to the support of learning, the learning effects and the achievement of the learning objectives.

The research questions include the following:

- Has the learning content been appropriately implemented in a way that promotes learning?
- Were the learning objectives achieved?
- How can this be determined? What indications are there for this?

For the latter, the instrument 'competence spider' can be used at SPP. The instrument can also be used in the context of an observed appraisal interview at SPP. For this purpose, an observation sheet is prepared. Subsequently, self-perception and external perception can be triangulated.

The evaluation aims to help us analyse if and when we can observe that the learners' interaction in the simulated 3-D world is able to produce meaning to the learner, which in other words means educational processes, that is, from the interaction in and with these virtual environments and objects. (cp. Reimann & Biazus, 2007, p.531)

Target groups:

- Newcomers to the company who are not yet familiar with the work processes and the operation of the machines required
- Target group skilled workers and machine operators who are familiar with the learning content

6 Research Methods

The quantitative research data will be collected through user surveys to be undertaken by students, staff and researchers.

The qualitative research methods include semi-structured interviews along the learning modules with the target groups of staff, preferably when using a learning environment. The instrument 'competence spider' will be used in a dialogue between employee and employer.

7 Conclusion

As the learner navigates around these imaginary spaces with different 3D objects, the exploration of the workplace becomes an experience for the learner rather than a theoretical perception of the workspace.

From the company's perspective, the 3D learning environment aims to support the onboarding processes and the reactivation of tacit knowledge transferable and work experience of staff. Last but not least the support of change and innovation processes inside of the organization is facilitated. However, the evaluation of the prototype will show whether the digital environment supports the learning process of newcomers in the company.

Potentially less tech-savvy people benefit from easy-to-learn handling of the devices, which enables their use in ageing-appropriate human-machine interaction design as well as process-related safeguarding and transfer of experiential knowledge. The latter has to be confirmed by the still outstanding evaluation of the pilot prototype. However, the didactic concept was challenged to a huge extent by technical limitations caused by low-cost solutions related to the budget of the research project in the development phase (focusing on 3D-modelling rather than AR).

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